

DISASTER-RELATED PSYCHOLOGICAL RESILIENCE AND SPIRITUAL WELL-BEING AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS FOLLOWING THE FEBRUARY 2023 KAHRAMANMARAŞ EARTHQUAKES: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY IN MALATYA, TÜRKİYE

Keywords

Disaster management,

Healthcare workers,

Psychological Resilience,

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ABSTRACT

Disasters are devastating events that profoundly disrupt the physical, economic, and social order of societies and can have long-lasting psychological effects on individuals. The February 6, 2023, Kahramanmaraş earthquakes constituted a large-scale disaster that had profound and multifaceted impacts not only on society as a whole but also on healthcare workers serving on the front lines of the disaster response. This study aims to evaluate psychological resilience and spiritual well-being among healthcare workers in Malatya Province. This descriptive, cross-sectional study was conducted between July and September 2024 with 265 healthcare workers employed at public hospitals in Malatya Province, which was severely affected by the February 6, 2023, Kahramanmaraş earthquakes, in a post-disaster context. The data collection process was conducted by the researcher using face-to-face interviews and an online survey. The Demographic Information Form, the Psychological Resilience Scale (PRS), and the Spiritual Well-Being Scale (SWBS) were used as data collection instruments in the study. The data obtained were analyzed using the SPSS 23.0 software package. The findings indicate that the vast majority of participants (90.9%) were present in the disaster area during the earthquake and were directly exposed to its devastating effects. In contrast, only 3.4% received psychological support after the disaster. Assessments conducted in the post-disaster context showed that psychological resilience and spiritual well-being varied according to demographic characteristics. In conclusion, these findings highlight the need to address psychological resilience and spiritual well-being among healthcare workers in the post-disaster period within a multidimensional framework. The effects of disaster exposure should be examined not only from a psychological standpoint but also in relation to spiritual and socio-demographic factors.

INTRODUCTION

Disasters are defined as disruptive events that affect either society as a whole or specific population groups, leading to physical, economic, and social losses, interrupting normal life, and exceeding local coping capacities¹. According to the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR), a disaster is defined as a serious disruption of the functioning of a community or society causing widespread human, material, economic, or environmental losses that exceed the affected community's capacity to cope using its own resources². In Türkiye, the Disaster and Emergency Management Presidency (AFAD) defines a disaster as: events of natural, human, or technological origin that affect the entire society or a segment thereof, cause physical, economic, and social losses, halt or disrupt normal life and human activities, and exceed local capacity; it also emphasizes that a disaster should be evaluated based on the consequences it produces rather than the event itself (AFAD, 2023)¹.

Disasters are generally classified into two main categories: natural and human-induced disasters³. Among natural disasters, earthquakes are among the most destructive. An earthquake is defined as the shaking caused on the Earth's surface by seismic waves resulting from the sudden release of energy accumulated in the Earth's crust. Earthquakes that occur in populated areas, in particular, deeply affect societies by causing not only loss of life but also significant material and emotional losses⁴.

It is well known that the impacts of earthquakes are becoming increasingly severe due to factors

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such as inadequate early warning systems, the sudden and unpredictable nature of earthquakes, rising population density, and increased settlement in high-risk areas. This has led to an increase in the number of people affected⁵. Despite accounting for only 0.5% of the world's land area, Türkiye is one of the countries at highest risk for earthquakes because of its location in an active tectonic zone and is ranked fourth worldwide in this respect⁶.

On February 6, 2023, at 04:17 and 13:24 local time in Türkiye, two major earthquakes with magnitudes of 7.7 and 7.6 occurred, with epicenters in Pazarcık (Kahramanmaraş) and Elbistan (Kahramanmaraş), respectively. These earthquakes affected a vast area of approximately 108,812 km², encompassing 11 provinces in the Eastern and Southeastern Anatolia regions, including Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Adıyaman, Kilis, Gaziantep, Malatya, Adana, Diyarbakır, Osmaniye, Elazığ, and Şanlıurfa, and resulted in significant loss of life and extensive structural damage. Referred to as the “disaster of the century,” these earthquakes rank among the most devastating disasters in the history of Türkiye¹. According to AFAD (2023) data, ground motion records and field observations indicate that the first earthquake had a more severe impact, particularly in Kahramanmaraş and Hatay, whereas the second earthquake had a more pronounced impact, mainly in Malatya and the surrounding provinces¹. According to the Ministry of Interior of the Republic of Türkiye (2023), these major disasters resulted in 53,537 deaths and 107,213 injuries⁷.

Psychological resilience is an important concept that refers to individuals' capacity to cope with challenging life events and stressful situations. Challenging life events can be a significant predisposing factor for psychological stress and disorders. However, reactions to such events can vary greatly from person to person. While one person experiencing the same adversity may maintain their functioning with only minimal, short-term distress, another may exhibit prolonged symptoms of psychological stress. These differences form a fundamental aspect of the concept of psychological resilience⁸.

Psychological resilience, as a concept that refers to an individual's capacity to adapt in the face of stress, trauma, challenges, and adverse life events, is an important area of research at both the individual and societal levels⁹. This capacity encompasses not only an individual's ability to survive in the face of challenges, but also their potential to

emerge from these experiences stronger¹⁰.

In their study of nurses, Çam and Büyükbayram (2017) reported a positive relationship between psychological resilience and emotional intelligence, and that this relationship enhances life satisfaction¹¹. Hoşoğlu and colleagues (2018), on the other hand, found that psychological resilience among teacher candidates varies according to sociodemographic variables such as gender and income level. When these findings are evaluated together, it becomes evident that psychological resilience is associated with individual and occupational variables and may serve as an important protective factor in determining the mental well-being of healthcare workers, particularly during times of crisis and disasters. This underscores the necessity of addressing the levels of psychological resilience and well-being among healthcare workers in the context of disasters¹².

In particular, Cevizci and Müezzini (2019) found that among healthcare workers, higher psychological resilience is associated with lower levels of psychological symptoms¹³. Similarly, Bozdağ and Ergün (2020) reported that psychological resilience among healthcare workers during the COVID-19 pandemic was positively associated with life satisfaction and perceived social support, whereas it decreased with increasing negative affect and anxiety. Furthermore, increasing age and professional experience were reported to strengthen coping skills¹⁴.

Spiritual well-being refers to the fulfillment of an individual's spiritual needs, in addition to their physical, emotional, and social needs, and plays an important role in improving quality of life. This concept is considered a supportive factor in helping individuals cope with loneliness, stress, depression, and psychosocial difficulties by helping them develop a more positive outlook in the face of challenging life events¹⁵. Rovers and Kocum (2010) associate spiritual well-being with inner peace arising from an individual's harmony with the universe, the discovery of meaning in life, hope, and a positive perception of life¹⁶.

Studies conducted on healthcare workers also highlight the importance of spiritual well-being. Kutlu, Ermin, and Aygün (2020) reported that intensive care nurses have high levels of spiritual well-being and that the perception of spiritual care plays an important role in this process¹⁷. Similarly, Yorulmaz

(2021) demonstrated that spiritual well-being increases with age among nurses and is associated with individual belief systems and job satisfaction¹⁸.

Healthcare workers are among the primary professional groups that take on key roles during disasters¹⁹. The need to maintain uninterrupted emergency medical response during large-scale disasters such as earthquakes, floods, or pandemics places an extraordinary burden on healthcare personnel. Indeed, according to data from the Ministry of Health following the February 6, 2023 Kahramanmaraş earthquakes, healthcare workers in the affected region not only fulfilled their professional responsibilities but also worked under extremely demanding conditions while being directly exposed to the effects of the disaster^{20,21}. During the disaster response, a substantial proportion of frontline healthcare personnel were actively involved in search and rescue operations, emergency interventions, and field healthcare services. According to official statements from the Ministry, thousands of healthcare workers, along with hundreds of ambulances and National Medical Rescue Team (UMKE) units, were deployed to the region, providing continuous healthcare services from the first day of the disaster^{20,22}. At the same time, it is emphasized that a significant portion of healthcare workers have suffered serious losses and damage in their own homes, yet they continue to perform their duties. Similarly, the literature reports a marked increase in symptoms of secondary traumatic stress, burnout, and psychological distress among professionals working in the field following natural disasters and mass traumatic events^{19,23,24}. In this context, understanding the mental health and well-being of healthcare workers in disaster settings—particularly in countries such as Türkiye located in active seismic zones—is of strategic importance not only for safeguarding individual well-being but also for strengthening disaster management systems and contributing to evidence-based policy development aimed at addressing future crises.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is an exploratory and descriptive quantitative study aimed at determining the levels of psychological resilience and spiritual well-being among healthcare workers serving in Malatya Province, which was severely affected by the February 6, 2023, Kahramanmaraş earthquakes.

The study population consisted of 13,282 healthcare workers employed in all public and private hospitals in Malatya Province. Participants were recruited using convenience sampling. The sample size was calculated using an expected frequency of 50%, a 90% confidence interval, and a 5% margin of error, yielding a required sample size of 265 participants. Data were collected between July 10 and September 15, 2024, from volunteer healthcare workers working at Doğanşehir Esra Köse Başaran State Hospital, Akçadağ Şehit Gökhan Arslan State Hospital, and Battalgazi State Hospital in Malatya who agreed to participate in the study and provided verbal informed consent. Data were collected from three public hospitals that granted institutional approval.

Data were collected by the researcher using face-to-face interviews and an online questionnaire. A structured questionnaire consisting of three sections was used in the study.

Demographic Information Form

This form includes information on participants' gender, age, educational level, professional title, length of employment, whether they were present in the region at the time of the earthquake, whether they experienced any loss during the earthquake, and whether they received psychological support after the earthquake.

Psychological Resilience Scale (PRS)

The scale, developed by Işık (2016), comprises 21 items and three sub-dimensions (commitment, control, and challenge). It is a 5-point Likert-type instrument, with total scores ranging from 21 to 105, and has a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.76.²⁵

Spiritual Well-Being Scale (SWBS)

Developed by Ekşi and Kardaş (2017), the scale consists of 29 items and three sub-dimensions: transcendence, harmony with nature, and anomie. It is a 5-point Likert-type scale, with a total Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.886²⁶.

The data were analyzed using SPSS 23.0. The internal consistency of the scales was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. The total Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the Psychological Resilience Scale (PRS) was 0.61; for the sub-dimensions, it was 0.67 for self-dedication, 0.82 for control, and 0.73 for

challenge. The total Cronbach’s alpha coefficient for the Spiritual Well-Being Scale (SWBS) was 0.86, with subscale coefficients of 0.86 for transcendence, 0.83 for harmony with nature, and 0.63 for anomic (loss of meaning). These values suggest acceptable internal consistency for both scales within the present study. The PRS demonstrated moderate internal consistency in the present sample.

The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test was used to assess normality, and the data were found not to be normally distributed. Therefore, non-parametric tests were used in all analyses. The Mann–Whitney U test was applied for comparisons between

two groups, while the Kruskal–Wallis test was used for comparisons among more than two groups. When significant differences were identified, Post hoc pairwise comparisons were performed using Dunn–Bonferroni tests. one-way ANOVA .

Prior to the study, ethical approval was obtained from the Scientific Research and Ethics Committee of Sivas Cumhuriyet University (May 23, 2024), along with institutional permission from the Malatya Provincial Health Directorate (July 10, 2024). Participation in the study was voluntary.

RESULTS

Table 1. Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Participants

Variables		n	%
Gender	Female	168	63.4
	Male	97	36.6
Age	25 Years and Under	41	15.5
	26–35 Years	117	44.2
	36–45 Years	57	21.5
	46 Years and Over	50	18.9
Education Level	High School	22	8.3
	Associate Degree	72	27.2
	Bachelor's Degree	131	49.4
	Postgraduate Degree	40	15.1
Occupational Title	Health Technician	57	21.5
	Medical Secretary	41	15.5
	Nurse/Midwife	91	34.3
	Physician	27	10.2
	Other	49	18.5
Work Experience (years)	≤ 5 Years	104	39.2
	6–15 Years	84	31.7
	16–25 Years	50	18.9
	≥ 26 Years	27	10.2
Presence in the Disaster Area During the Earthquake	Yes	241	90.9
	No	24	9.1
Bereavement Due to the Earthquake	Yes	44	16.6
	No	221	83.4
Receiving Psychological Support	Yes	9	3.4
	No	256	96.6

A total of 265 healthcare professionals participated in the study, including 168 females (63.4%) and 97 males (36.6%). Nearly half of the participants (44.2%) were aged between 26 and 35 years, 49.4% held a bachelor's degree, and 34.3% were employed as nurse-midwives. In terms of characteristics, most participants (90.9%) were present in the disaster area during the earthquake, 16.6% reported experiencing a loss, and only 3.4% received psychological support following the earthquake. Work experience and other disaster-related variables are presented in Table 1.

Table 2. Comparison of Psychological Resilience Scale (PRS) and Spiritual Well-Being Scale (SWBS) Subscale Scores by Gender (Mann–Whitney U Test)

Scale Subdimensions	Female (Median)	Male (Median)	Mann–Whitney U	p-value
PRS – Commitment	3.64	3.57	7592	0.35
PRS – Control	3.57	3.43	7299	0.16
PRS – Challenge	3.86	3.86	7891	0.67
SWBS – Transcendence	4.53	4.07	6423	0.0001*
SWBS – Harmony with Nature	4.36	4.00	6636	0.01*
SWBS – Anomie	2.86	2.86	7426	0.23

The Mann–Whitney U test by gender showed no statistically significant differences in the PRS subdimensions ($p > 0.05$). In contrast, females had significantly higher scores in the SWBS subdimensions of transcendence ($p < 0.001$) and harmony with nature ($p = 0.01$) ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3. Comparison of Psychological Resilience Scale (PRS) and Spiritual Well-Being Scale (SWBS) Subscale Scores by Age Groups (Kruskal–Wallis Test)

Scale Subdimensions	≤25 (Median)	26–35 years (Median)	36–45 years (Median)	≥46 years (Median)	Kruskal–Wallis H	p-value
PRS – Commitment	3.71	3.57	3.57	3.50	2.938	0.40
PRS – Control	3.71	3.57	3.71	3.43	8.414	0.04*
PRS – Challenge	4.29	3.86	3.71	3.64	23.665	$p < 0.001$
SWBS – Transcendence	4.53	4.20	4.47	4.37	2.884	0.41
SWBS – Harmony with Nature	4.14	4.14	4.43	4.36	4.152	0.25
SWBS – Anomie	2.86	2.86	2.71	2.80	0.899	0.83

* $p < 0,05$

Significant age-related differences were observed in the PRS Control ($H = 8.414$, $p = 0.04$) and Challenge ($H = 23.665$, $p < 0.001$) subdimensions. Post hoc pairwise comparisons indicated that participants aged ≤25 years had significantly higher Control and Challenge scores than older age groups. No significant age-related differences were observed in the SWBS subdimensions (all $p > 0.05$). No statistically significant differences were found in any of the PRS or SWBS subdimensions according to professional title ($p > 0.05$).

Table 4. PRS and SWBS Subscale Scores by Loss Experience During the Earthquake (Mann–Whitney U Test)

Scale Subdimensions	Experiencing Loss (Median)	No Loss (Median)	Mann–Whitney U	p
PRS – Commitment	3.43	3.57	4360	0.28
PRS – Control	3.29	3.57	3904	0.04*
PRS – Challenge	3.64	3.86	4015	0.07
SWBS – Transcendence	4.23	4.40	4838	0.96
SWBS – Harmony with Nature	4.43	4.29	4455	0.38
SWBS – Anomie	3.00	2.86	4247	0.18

According to Table 4, healthcare workers who experienced loss during the earthquake had significantly lower scores on the PRS control subdimension compared with those who did not

experience loss ($p = 0.04$). No significant differences were observed in the SWBS subdimensions (all $p > 0.05$).

Table 5. PRS and SWBS Subscale Scores by Post-Earthquake Psychological Support Status (Mann–Whitney U Test)

Scale Subdimensions	Received Psychological Support (n = 9) (Median)	No Psychological Support (n = 256) (Median)	Mann–Whitney U	p
PRS – Commitment	3.43	3.57	1137	0.95
PRS – Control	4.00	3.57	855	0.19
PRS – Challenge	3.86	3.86	1011	0.53
SWBS – Transcendence	4.73	4.33	753	0.08
SWBS – Harmony with Nature	4.71	4.29	684	0.04*
SWBS – Anomie	2.86	2.86	1041	0.62

* $p < 0,05$

Healthcare workers who received psychological support after the earthquake ($n = 9$) had significantly higher scores on the SWBS Harmony with Nature subscale than those who did not receive psychological support ($n = 256$) (median: 4.71 vs. 4.29;

$U = 684.0$, $p = 0.04$). No significant differences were observed in the PRS subscales or the remaining SWBS subscales (all $p > 0.05$).

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics for PRS and SWBS Subscales

Scale	Scale Subdimensions	Min–Max	Mean \pm SD
PRS	Commitment	1.57–5.00	3.57 \pm 0.60
	Control	1.29–5.00	3.57 \pm 0.62
	Challenge	1.14–5.00	3.86 \pm 0.71
SWBS	Transcendence	1.00–5.00	4.33 \pm 0.67
	Harmony with Nature	1.29–5.00	4.29 \pm 0.64
	Anomie	1.00–5.00	2.86 \pm 0.85

Healthcare workers' psychological resilience levels were in the moderate-to-high range (mean: 3.57–3.86), while spiritual well-being scores were high in the transcendence and harmony with nature subdimensions (mean: 4.29–4.33). The anomie subdimension reflects a perceived loss of meaning, purpose, and coherence in life and represents a sense of emptiness or lack of direction. In this study, the mean score for anomie remained low (mean: 2.86).

CONCLUSION

Earthquakes are among the most frequent and destructive natural disasters worldwide. On February 6, 2023, two major earthquakes with epicenters in Kahramanmaraş (Pazarcık, Mw 7.7) and Elbistan (Mw 7.6) struck Türkiye, affecting 11 provinces. The disaster resulted in more than 50,000 deaths and hundreds of thousands of injuries and was described as the “disaster of the century”²⁷. Large-scale disasters affect different groups in society in different ways, but their impact is especially strong on professionals who play critical roles, such as healthcare workers. Healthcare workers often experience a double burden: they are directly affected by the disaster along with their families, while at the same time they are expected to continue providing uninterrupted healthcare services. This dual responsibility can place considerable psychological and professional strain on them.

The findings of this study show that healthcare workers in Malatya Province—one of the regions severely affected by the February 6, 2023, Kahramanmaraş earthquakes—were impacted by the disaster both professionally and personally. The fact that most participants (90.9%) were in the disaster area during the earthquake and that about one in six (16.6%) experienced the loss of a close relative indicates direct exposure to the event. In contrast, only 3.4% of healthcare workers reported receiving psychological support after the earthquake, which is a notable finding. This points to important gaps in access to, or utilization of, mental health services among healthcare workers in the post-disaster period. These findings may inform disaster preparedness programs aimed at strengthening psychological resilience and spiritual well-being among healthcare workers.

Our study found that healthcare workers' psychological resilience levels were generally moderate to high, while their spiritual well-being levels were high, particularly in the transcendence and harmony with nature subdimensions. When

examining the subdimensions of psychological resilience, participants scored highest in the challenge dimension, whereas self-dedication and control scores were relatively lower. These findings suggest that healthcare workers have a strong capacity to adapt to and cope with stressful events such as disasters; however, prolonged stress may more strongly affect their sense of control and commitment to work.

The findings of our study show partial discrepancies with those reported in previous studies^{24, 28, 29, 30}. However, it is important to note that none of these studies were conducted in the post-disaster period following a major earthquake, which provides an important context for interpreting these differences. In this respect, our study offers a unique contribution by examining psychological resilience among healthcare workers in the aftermath of a large-scale disaster.

Our study also found that younger healthcare workers and those with less professional experience exhibited higher levels of psychological resilience. In particular, the challenge and control subscales of the psychological resilience scale reflect individuals' cognitive appraisal of stressful situations. The higher scores observed among younger employees may be associated with a more flexible, open-minded, and optimistic outlook toward the future, which may help explain this finding. One possible explanation for this finding is that older healthcare workers may have greater family and financial responsibilities, which could increase psychological burden during disasters. The fact that individuals who are older and have more professional experience are more likely to be married and have children can lead to intense “family-related anxiety” in addition to individual anxiety during disasters. Furthermore, the risk of losing—or the potential to lose—the financial assets this group has accumulated over the years serves as an additional source of stress that can exacerbate the psychological burden of a disaster. When all these variables are considered together, the finding that younger healthcare workers exhibit higher levels of psychological resilience can be viewed as a reasonable outcome within the context of this study.

Regarding spiritual well-being, the findings of this study suggest that healthcare workers are able to maintain psychological balance through spiritual resources such as meaning in life, hope, and harmony with nature. In particular, the low level of anomie indicates that participants largely preserved their sense of meaning and purpose in life. These

findings suggest that spiritual well-being may act as a protective psychological factor in the context of traumatic events such as disasters.

The literature reports varying results regarding the age variable. While some studies have reported that psychological resilience decreases with increasing age or is higher among younger individuals^{31,32}, other studies have found no significant association between age and psychological resilience³³⁻³⁵.

In contrast, some studies have reported that psychological resilience increases with age^{36,37,38}. Similarly, in the literature on spiritual well-being, age, life experience, and individual belief systems appear to exert varying degrees of influence. Taken together, these findings suggest that psychological resilience and spiritual well-being cannot be explained by age alone; rather, they are shaped by the interaction of disaster exposure, professional experience, social support, and individual coping strategies. In particular, among healthcare professionals working in disaster settings, these factors should be considered alongside both occupational responsibilities and personal traumatic experiences.

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that resilience training programs, including both theoretical education and practical applications, be incorporated into the training and professional development of healthcare workers to help them better cope with traumatic situations such as disasters. It is also important to assess healthcare workers' psychological resilience and spiritual well-being at regular intervals and to provide timely psychosocial support when needed, particularly for those at higher risk.

In addition, institutions should develop measures to ensure the safety of healthcare workers and, when possible, their families during disasters. Practical administrative support such as leave arrangements and temporary reassignment of duties should be prioritized for affected staff. Providing temporary accommodation during disaster periods may also help reduce psychological burden and support the continuity of healthcare services. A limitation of this study is that it was conducted only among healthcare workers in Malatya Province, which limits the generalizability of the findings to the wider healthcare workforce.

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Conflicts of interest statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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